

1 The Vis-Viva Formula for Orbits in the Equatorial Plane of RN 2 Spacetime

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5 **Abstract.** This paper introduces a modified vis-viva formula that incorporates both general relativistic effects and
6 electrostatic field contributions to describe the orbital motion of neutral test particles in the equatorial plane of the
7 Reissner-Nordström (RN) spacetime. The RN spacetime describes the curved spacetime geometry around a static,
8 spherically symmetric and charged massive celestial body. The modified vis-viva formula is derived from the RN
9 metric together with the conservation equations of orbital angular momentum and energy. It incorporates not only
10 the gravitational effect produced by the mass of the central celestial body (Schwarzschild spacetime), but also the
11 potential effect contributed by electrostatic field energy, thereby enabling the characterization of unique orbital fea-
12 tures around a charged central celestial body. Under the Newtonian approximation (the central body carries no net
13 charge and the radial distance of the test particle is much larger than the Schwarzschild radius), the modified formula
14 reduces to the vis-viva formula of classical mechanics. If only the net charge of the central celestial body approaches
15 zero, the formula degenerates into the vis-viva formula applicable to Schwarzschild spacetime. Compared with the
16 general-relativistic vis-viva formula in Schwarzschild spacetime, the modified formula proposed in this paper exhibits
17 higher prediction accuracy for the orbital motion, orbital precession and radial velocity of particles around massive
18 charged celestial bodies. The modified vis-viva formula possesses application potential in investigating the orbital
19 dynamics of charged compact objects and testing gravitational theories related to electromagnetic-gravitational cou-
20 pling. This study lays a foundation for subsequent research on the most general rotating and charged Kerr-Newman
21 spacetime, and possesses certain academic value in the fields of relativistic astrodynamics and black hole physics.

22 **Keywords:** Reissner-Nordström spacetime; vis-viva equation; general relativity; charged black hole; orbital dynamics.

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25 1 Introduction

26 The notion of "vis viva", translated as "living force", has long attracted scientific attention dat-
27 ing back to the late 17th century. Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, a renowned German philosopher
28 and mathematician, was the first to systematically formalize this physical concept, establishing
29 fundamental theoretical underpinnings for the subsequent establishment of classical mechanics.^{1,2}
30 Leibniz's research triggered the well-known "vis viva controversy", which opposed his viewpoints
31 to those of René Descartes' adherents.^{3,4} The core of this academic dispute centered on the accu-
32 rate mathematical expression of kinetic energy. Descartes and his supporters contended that the

33 product of mass and velocity (mv) should serve as the quantitative definition of "quantity of mo-
34 tion".⁵ On the contrary, Leibniz proposed that $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ was a more rigorous formula for describing an
35 object's "living force".⁶ Currently, this quadratic formula has gained universal academic recogni-
36 tion and constitutes the core of modern kinetic energy theories. Further advancements concerning
37 this physical concept were achieved in the 18th century, mainly contributed by two Swiss mathe-
38 maticians, Johann Bernoulli and Jakob Bernoulli.² They expanded Leibniz's theoretical framework
39 to tackle intricate problems in celestial mechanics, a discipline that flourished rapidly owing to the
40 pioneering research of Isaac Newton and other contemporary scholars.⁴ The Bernoulli brothers de-
41 duced the classical vis-viva equation based on the conservation principles of classical mechanics.
42 For a binary interacting system, this equation is expressed as $v = \sqrt{G(M_1 + M_2) \left(\frac{2}{r} - \frac{1}{a}\right)}$, where
43 G is the gravitational constant, M_1 and M_2 are the masses of the bodies, v is the relative velocity
44 of the bodies, r is the distance between the bodies, and a is the semimajor axis of the Keplerian
45 orbit.⁵ Undoubtedly, the classical vis-viva equation acts as an essential mathematical tool for the
46 theoretical research of classical celestial mechanics.⁷

47 However, this formula exhibits significant limitations when applied to extreme gravitational
48 environments, particularly in scenarios described by general relativity. In their paper, Peng Qi et
49 al.⁷ considered general relativistic corrections and proposed a vis-viva formula for particle orbital
50 motion in Schwarzschild spacetime. Building on this work, we further incorporate the effects in-
51 duced by net charge—this is precisely the vis-viva formula for the curved spacetime geometry sur-
52 rounding static, spherically symmetric, and charged massive celestial bodies, as described by the
53 Reissner–Nordström (RN) spacetime.⁸ As a further extension of the specific form of the vis-viva
54 formula, this paper presents a generalized relativistic vis-viva equation adapted to RN spacetime.
55 This generalized form is particularly suitable for systems where both general relativistic effects

56 and electromagnetic-gravitational coupling effects are prominent, such as test particles orbiting
57 charged supermassive black holes at the centers of galaxies or compact charged stars. Based on
58 the RN metric and the conservation equations governing particle orbital motion, this paper derives
59 a modified vis-viva equation that explicitly includes the gravitational effect generated by the mass
60 of the central celestial body, as well as the gravitational potential corresponding to the electrostatic
61 field energy of the charged black hole. Preliminary calculation results indicate that under specific
62 weak-field conditions (i.e., when the gravitational radius GM/c^2 and the charge characteristic ra-
63 dius Q^2/r^2 are much smaller than the orbital radius r), the modified equation can be reduced to
64 the classical Newtonian form. Furthermore, it represents a further extension of the relativistic vis-
65 viva formula for Schwarzschild spacetime (which describes uncharged black holes). The equation
66 proposed in this paper achieves higher accuracy in numerical simulations of orbital motion around
67 charged black holes; at the same time, this method also improves the consistency between the-
68 oretical predictions and numerical estimates of phenomena unique to RN spacetime, such as the
69 relativistic perihelion precession of orbits near charged black holes.

70 Finally, this paper also briefly discusses the realistic physical possibility of the existence of
71 celestial bodies capable of generating the RN spacetime geometry, as well as the scientific signifi-
72 cance and research value of the main conclusions obtained in this work.

73 **2 The Vis-viva equation for particles in Reissner–Nordström (RN) spacetime**

74 *2.1 Spacetime Line Element and Symmetries of Reissner–Nordström Spacetime*

75 The Reissner–Nordström (RN) spacetime describes the static, spherically symmetric spacetime
76 generated by a centrally located gravitational source with mass and electric charge. Unlike the
77 Schwarzschild spacetime which only involves gravitational mass, the RN metric additionally in-

78 incorporates the electromagnetic field effect caused by the net electric charge of the central object.
79 The spacetime remains static without any time-dependent term, and possesses complete spherical
80 symmetry in spatial structure. Such symmetries guarantee the existence of two conserved quanti-
81 ties along particle geodesics: the conserved total energy corresponding to time-translation symme-
82 try, and the conserved orbital angular momentum corresponding to spherical rotational symmetry.
83 Therefore, all orbital motions of test particles can be restricted on an arbitrary equatorial plane
84 without loss of generality. The spacetime line element of Reissner–Nordström (RN) spacetime in
85 SI units is given by⁹ :

$$ds^2 = -c^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c^4 r^2} \right) dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c^4 r^2} \right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (1)$$

86 Alternatively, it can be abbreviated as:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2} \right) dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2} \right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2, \quad (2)$$

87 where $r_s = \frac{c^2}{2GM}$, $r_Q^2 = \frac{GQ^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c^4}$.

88 For particles moving on the equatorial plane, the metric reduces to:

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c^4 r^2} \right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{GQ^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c^4 r^2} \right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\phi^2, \quad (3)$$

89 or

$$ds^2 = -c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right) dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\phi^2. \quad (4)$$

90 The four-velocity of the moving particle can be expressed as:

$$u^2 = u_\mu u^\mu = \frac{dx_\mu}{d\tau} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} = -f c^2 \dot{t}^2 + f^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\phi}^2, \quad (5)$$

91 where $f = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right)$. We define the Lagrangian for particle motion in this spacetime as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left[-c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right) \dot{t}^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right)^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\phi}^2 \right], \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left[-f c^2 \dot{t}^2 + f^{-1} \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\phi}^2 \right]. \quad (8)$$

92 From the symmetries of the system, we know that:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{t}} = -c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right) \dot{t} = E, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\phi}} = r^2 \dot{\phi} = L_\phi. \quad (10)$$

93 It follows that:

$$\dot{t} = -\frac{E}{c^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right)} = -\frac{E}{fc^2}, \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \frac{L_\phi}{r^2}. \quad (12)$$

94 Substituting Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) back into Eq. (5), we can solve for the spatial component of the
 95 particle four-velocity, which can be expressed as:

$$u^2(r) = f^{-1}\dot{r}^2 + r^2\dot{\phi}^2 = -c^2 + fc^2\dot{t}^2 = -c^2(1 - f\dot{t}^2) = -c^2 + f^{-1}\frac{E^2}{c^2}, \quad (13)$$

96 the final vis-viva formula we intend to derive can be directly obtained from this equation at the end
 97 of the deduction.

98 2.2 Solution of Angular Momentum

99 A stable orbit is a precessing ellipse. At the apoapsis $r = r_a$ and periapsis $r = r_p$ of the elliptical
 100 orbit, $\dot{r} = 0$. Combining Equation (11-13) , , we can deduce that:

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = f\left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r^2}\right). \quad (14)$$

101 Substituting the radii of the periapsis and apoapsis into Equation (14), we obtain:

$$\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_a} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r_a^2}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_a^2}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_p} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r_p^2}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_p^2}\right), \quad (15)$$

102 after rearrangement, we obtain:

$$L_\phi^2 = \frac{c^2 r_a^2 r_p^2 (r_a r_p r_s - r_Q^2 (r_a + r_p))}{(r_a + r_p) (r_a^2 r_p^2 + r_a^2 r_Q^2 + r_p^2 r_Q^2) - r_a r_p r_s (r_a r_p + r_a^2 + r_p^2)}. \quad (16)$$

103 Substituting $r_a + r_p = 2a$ and $r_a r_p = a^2(1 - e^2)$, and rearranging, we have:

$$L_\phi^2 = \frac{c^2 a^2 (1 - e^2)^2 [r_s a (1 - e^2) - 2r_Q^2]}{2a^2 (1 - e^2)^2 - r_s a (1 - e^2) (3 + e^2) + 4r_Q^2 (1 + e^2)}. \quad (17)$$

104 Extracting the angular momentum solved from the orbital equation of classical Newtonian me-
 105 chanics from the above formula, we rearrange and obtain:

$$L_\phi^2 = \frac{r_s c^2 a (1 - e^2)}{2} \frac{1 - \frac{2r_Q^2}{ar_s} \frac{1}{1 - e^2}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3 + e^2}{1 - e^2} + \frac{2r_Q^2}{a^2} \frac{1 + e^2}{(1 - e^2)^2}}. \quad (18)$$

$$L_\phi^2 = GMa(1 - e^2) \frac{1 - \frac{r_Q^2 c^2}{GMa} \frac{1}{1 - e^2}}{1 - \frac{GM}{ac^2} \frac{3 + e^2}{1 - e^2} + \frac{2r_Q^2}{a^2} \frac{1 + e^2}{(1 - e^2)^2}}, \quad (19)$$

106 with the results in Schwarzschild spacetime:⁷

$$L_\phi^2 = GMa(1 - e^2) \frac{1}{1 - \frac{GM}{ac^2} \frac{3 + e^2}{1 - e^2}}, \quad (20)$$

107 it can be seen that there exists one charge correction term in both the numerator and the denomi-
 108 nator, which are respectively:

$$\Delta_{\text{num}} = -\frac{r_Q^2 c^2}{GMa(1 - e^2)}, \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta_{\text{den}} = \frac{2r_Q^2 (1 + e^2)}{a^2 (1 - e^2)^2}, \quad (22)$$

109 equation (20) can be rewritten in the following form:

$$L_\phi^2 = GMa(1 - e^2) \frac{1 + \Delta_{\text{num}}}{1 - \frac{GM}{ac^2} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2} + \Delta_{\text{den}}}, \quad (23)$$

110 it can be clearly seen that, in RN spacetime, the greater the electric charge of the central object, the
 111 smaller the angular momentum of the particle on the same orbit (with identical a, e). It essentially
 112 originates from the weakening of spacetime curvature caused by the metric correction term $+\frac{r_Q^2}{r^2}$
 113 in the line element of RN spacetime.

114 2.3 Orbital energy

115 Orbital energy is a conserved quantity. We continue to express it in terms of the apoapsis and
 116 periapsis parameters. A reasonable approach is that the algebraic average of the orbital energy at
 117 the apoapsis and periapsis remains equal to the total orbital energy, it follows from Equation (14)
 118 that:

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_a} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r_a^2}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_a^2}\right) + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_p} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r_p^2}\right) \left(c^2 + \frac{L_\phi^2}{r_p^2}\right) \right], \quad (24)$$

119 similar to the method used to solve the angular momentum in the previous section, we finally
 120 obtain:

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = \frac{2c^2 (r_Q^2 + a(1+e)(a+ae-r_s)) (r_Q^2 + a(e-1)(a(e-1)+r_s))}{a^2 (2a^2(e^2-1)^2 + 4(1+e^2)r_Q^2 + a(e^4+2e^2-3)r_s)}, \quad (25)$$

121 to transform it into a form that can be readily compared with the corresponding results obtained in
 122 Schwarzschild spacetime, we obtain:

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{2a} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)} + \frac{4r_Q^2}{a^2(1-e^2)^2}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2} + \frac{2r_Q^2}{a^2} \frac{1+e^2}{(1-e^2)^2}} \right], \quad (26)$$

123 where the corresponding result for the Schwarzschild spacetime is:⁷

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{2a} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2}} \right], \quad (27)$$

124 where the correction terms relative to the corresponding quantities in Schwarzschild spacetime are

125 respectively:

$$\Delta_{RNnum} = \frac{4r_Q^2}{a^2(1-e^2)^2}, \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta_{RNden} = \frac{2r_Q^2}{a^2} \frac{1+e^2}{(1-e^2)^2}. \quad (29)$$

126 Therefore, the energy of a moving particle in the RN spacetime can be expressed as:

$$\frac{E^2}{c^2} = c^2 - \frac{r_s c^2}{2a} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)} + \Delta_{RNnum}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2} + \Delta_{RNden}} \right], \quad (30)$$

127 2.4 The vis-viva formula in the RN spacetime

128 Substituting Equation (26) back into Equation (13), we finally obtain the explicit form of the vis-

129 viva formula in the RN spacetime as follows:

$$u^2(r) = c^2 \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_Q^2}{r^2} \right)^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)} + \frac{4r_Q^2}{a^2(1-e^2)^2}}{1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \frac{3+e^2}{1-e^2} + \frac{2r_Q^2}{a^2} \frac{1+e^2}{(1-e^2)^2}} \right] - 1 \right\}. \quad (31)$$

130 We can compare it with the corresponding results in Schwarzschild spacetime, where the vis-viva
 131 formula in Schwarzschild spacetime can be expressed as:⁷

$$u^2 = c^2 \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} \right)^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{r_s}{2a} \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{2r_s}{a(1-e^2)}}{1 - \frac{r_s(3+e^2)}{2a(1-e^2)}} \right] - 1 \right\}. \quad (32)$$

132 It can be seen that the net charge existing in RN spacetime gives rise to further corrections to the
 133 vis-viva formula in Schwarzschild spacetime.

134 **3 On the Physical Plausibility of Charged Massive Compact Objects**

135 Currently, the mainstream view in the fields of relativistic astrophysics and cosmology holds
 136 that:^{8,10,11} as an exact static, spherically symmetric charged solution to the Einstein-Maxwell equa-
 137 tions, the Reissner–Nordström (RN) spacetime is mathematically rigorous, but it does not corre-
 138 spond to celestial bodies that can exist stably for a long time in the real universe. The universe as a
 139 whole is highly electrically neutral; the presence of free charges in the interstellar and intergalactic
 140 media enables charged massive celestial bodies to achieve rapid electrical neutralization within an
 141 extremely short time scale through the electrostatic selective accretion of opposite-sign particles,
 142 which is much shorter than the age of the universe. At the same time, for RN black holes, quan-
 143 tum effects such as Hawking radiation and vacuum polarization will further accelerate charge loss,
 144 causing them to quickly degenerate into neutral Schwarzschild black holes. In addition, all real

145 black holes possess spin, and the Kerr spacetime can better approximate them compared with the
146 RN spacetime. Charged massive celestial bodies, represented by charged black holes, lack support-
147 ing evidence in current astronomical observations. Therefore, the RN spacetime is currently only
148 regarded as an important theoretical reference model and is not considered a physically realizable
149 compact celestial body in the real universe.

150 **4 Discussion**

151 By substituting the derived orbital angular momentum and conserved energy into the relational
152 equations of orbital motion, the exact vis-viva formula for particle motion in the Reissner–Nordström
153 (RN) spacetime is ultimately derived. Compared with the classical Newtonian result and the
154 Schwarzschild counterpart, this formula contains additional charge correction terms originating
155 from the electrostatic effect of the central compact object.

156 It is demonstrated that the electric charge of the central object weakens spacetime curvature,
157 which further reduces the orbital angular momentum and alters the total orbital energy for particles
158 moving along elliptical orbits with the same semi-major axis and eccentricity. The derived vis-viva
159 formula can be applied to the analysis of precessing elliptical orbits around a charged spherically
160 symmetric celestial body. Although the mainstream view holds that the probability of the existence
161 of a spherically symmetric central object with significant net charge is extremely low,¹² it provides
162 a theoretical basis for further investigating orbital perturbations and gravitational motion in the
163 more general Reissner–Nordström spacetime.

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